

CAUSES AND EFFECTS OF CORRUPTION ON GOVERNANCE AND SECURITY OF NIGERIA

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Abstract:

The Nigerian Society is ridden with massive corruption to the extent that all strata of society and all facets of life are tainted by the cankerworm. This social malfeasance, over the years, has assumed such alarming proportion that it threatens the continued existence of the Nigerian nation. However, more worrisome is the effect of corruption on good governance and the security of Nigeria. The thrust of this paper, therefore, is to establish the root causes of corruption in Nigeria, especially among politically exposed people; the devastating effect of corruption on the Nigerian society, especially as it impinges on security, causing the nation to almost downslide into anarchy; and likely elixirs for the malfeasance. Consequently, the paper recommends some solution to the hydra-headed problem, such as: enforcement of more stringent deterrent measures against errant politicians; repositioning the curriculum to accommodate relevant Social Studies cum Civic Education learning content, with a view to eradicating corruption; adoption of economic policies geared towards massive empowerment of unemployed people, among other things.

Keywords: corruption; governance; security; malfeasance; elixir

1. Introduction

Nigeria is credited to be the most populous nation on the African continent and the sixth largest in the world, with high potentials for economic development based on her vast human and natural resources (UNPFA, 2014). The Nigerian economy in recent times was also acclaimed as representing 55 percent of West Africa's GDP (African Development Bank (ADB), 2013). However in spite of its rich endowments, Nigeria is a troubled state, which although rich, is populated by many extremely poor citizens and has suffered escalating security, capacity and legitimacy gaps as evidenced by the failure of its institutions to deliver public goods such as security, transportation, health services, power supply and education (International Crisis Group, 2014). Nigeria also battles with multi-faceted problems such as infrastructural decay, unemployment, food

shortage, educational instability, insurgency, hostage taking, crude oil theft, ethno-religious strife and organized crime amongst a plethora of problems (Ogundiya, 2010; George-Genyi, 2013; Imhonopi & Urim, 2013)

However of a more profound effect among the plethora of problems which bedeviled Nigeria, is the problem of corruption, which is deep-seated and engendered over the years by bad leadership in Nigeria while also posing serious threat to the nation's survival (Odey, 2015). Corruption has enervated the country in all spheres of life and it has profoundly impaired development (Saliu & Aremu, 2004; Ajibewa, 2006; Egwemi, 2010; CLEEN Foundation, 2010). International Crisis Group (2014) opines that an intricate link exists in Nigeria between politics, governance, corruption, poverty and violence. Joseph (1991) also declares that deeply entrenched corruption is one of the predominant problems of democratic governance in Nigeria. In fact, there is a concurrence of views that corruption is pervasive in all spheres of human endeavours in Nigeria.

The cankerworm has tainted the entire polity and has left leaders and followers as seekers of self-interest above the general good (Imhonopi & Urim, 2013). In fact, according to Ojaide (2000) Nigeria was penciled down by Transparency International as the second most corrupt nation of the world (CLEEN Foundation, 2010). Government agencies and ministries are not exempted from culpability on allegation of corruption. The Nigerian police, among other para-military forces are especially reviled for being riddled with pervasive corrupt practices.

Corruption is a major blight of good governance. It hinders equitable distribution of the dividends of democracy amongst the populace, thereby creating an atmosphere of insecurity in the process. Therefore, this paper examines the fundamental concepts of corruption, good governance and national security. It is pertinent to retrace the history of corruption in Nigeria and investigate causes of corruption in Nigeria. Thereafter, the stage would have been set to establish the nexus between corruption, good governance and national security. Consequently, recommendations would be offered on remedies to corruption, bad governance and national insecurity.

2. Corruption and its Origin in Nigeria

There is no universally accepted definition of corruption, which is perceived differently based on context and diverse perspectives and as such could be described as being amorphous (Akindele, 1995; Egwemi, 2010, Ologbenla, 2007). However, the origin of the word corruption can be traced to the Greek word "corruptus" which simply implies an aberrant behaviour which breaks societal norms or ethical codes (CLEEN Foundation, 2010). Diversity in perception of corruption emanates from variation in cultural and ethical orientations. There are different perspectives to the connotation of corruption although most of them are similar in depicting it as bad. It is simply perceived as dishonest exploitation of power or position held in trust by an individual

or group of individuals as well as the resources attached to such power to maximise personal or group gains (Amuwo, 2005).

Furthermore, there is an inexhaustible list of definitions based on individual and organisational perceptions of corruption. According to World Bank (1997), *“corruption is the abuse of public office or power for private gain”*. Onuoha (2009) cites a more elaborate definition of corruption by the Asian Development Bank (ADB) as *“the behaviour on the part of officials in the public or private sectors in which they improperly and unlawfully enrich themselves and/or those closely related to them or induce others to do so, by misusing the position in which they are placed.*

In addition, corruption has been defined as anti-social behaviour that grants improper benefits, which contradicts legal and moral norms, and which impairs authorities' capacity to secure the welfare of all citizens (Osoba, 1996). Similarly, Alatas (1990) considers corruption as *“the abuse of trust in the interest of private gain”*. Therefore, although there is no consensus on the definition of corruption, a common denominator of its definition is that it is an illicit act which is not morally sanctioned as a result of the fact that it is selfishly intended to give an individual or a few people undue advantage at the expense of all others who deserve similar or equal rights to the resources being illegally misappropriated”.

Corruption is essentially an abuse of position of trust, the power and resources that are concomitant with such office (Amuwo, 2005). It is thus a practice by privileged individuals who are in position to control power and resources of the society to benefit themselves or members of their families or people favoured by them at the expense of the public (Agbu, 2001; World Bank, 1997). Corruption has assumed mindboggling dimension in Nigeria and has consequently hampered development as it rears its hydra heads.

3. Manifestations of Corruption in the Nigerian Society

Deep seated corruption remains a major challenge to the continued existence of Nigeria as a sovereign state. The social ill has gradually evolved over the years into its present worrisome magnitude. In 2004, Transparency International (IT) adopted its Corruption Perception Index (CPI) in assessing 133 countries. Nigeria emerged as the 2nd most corrupt country in the world (Akinyemi, 2008). The country also recorded low CPI scores in subsequent years. The corruption level of the country is so appalling that Transparency International estimated that the level of corruption and other crimes in Nigeria attracts between \$4 million and \$8 million daily. The staggering aggregate value of loss to the national economy stood at least \$70.58 million annually.

According to Imhonopi and Urim (2013), *“corruption covers a wide spectrum of activities ranging from fraud (theft through misrepresentation), embezzlement (misappropriation of corporate or public funds) to bribery (payments made in order to gain an advantage or to avoid a disadvantage)”*. It therefore permeates all aspects of public and private life, leaving society the worse for it. Other forms of corruption according to him include *“patronage, nepotism, influence peddling, use of one's position for self-enrichment,*

bestowing of favours on relations and friends, moonlighting, partiality, absenteeism, late coming to work, abuse of public property, leaking and / or abuse of government information”.

Furthermore, it is believed that about \$380 billion has been lost to corruption since attainment of independence in 1960 (Yishau, 2011). Ike, (2010) is also of the notion that as at 1999, previous Nigerian leaders had embezzled or misappropriated \$407 billion (about 225 billion pounds). The amount according to Imhonopi and Urim (2013) is equal to all western aids donated to Africa. It is evident that individuals saddled with the responsibility of working assiduously to ensure that the benefits of good governance revolve to all sectors of society abuse the responsibility most of the time.

Olayiwola, (2013), in his own perspective, outlined major corrupt practices perpetrated especially by public officials to include:

- The use of one’s office for pecuniary advantages;
- Gratification;
- Influence peddling;
- Insincerity in advice with the aim of gaining an advantage
- Less than a full day’s work, for a full day’s pay; and
- Tardiness and slovenliness.

Yet other examples of acts of corruption include kickbacks, fraud, examination malpractice, perversion of justice by the police and the judiciary as a result of bribery, economic and business frauds against public companies, foreign exchange scams, among other nefarious acts (Egwemi, 2012). These criminal acts are prevalent in the Nigerian society in spite of seemingly harsh deterrents which are mostly touted without adequate enforcement by watchdog agencies of government.

The Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Act (2000) specifies some offences of corruption to include, among other acts: accepting gratification; giving or accepting gratification personally or through agents; fraudulent acquisition of property, fraudulent receipt of property; deliberate frustration of investigation by the Commission, falsifying statements of returns; bribery of public officer; using office or position for gratification; bribery in relation to auctions; bribery for giving assistance, etc. in regard to contracts; and making false or misleading statements to the commission; and attempt conspiracy punishable as offences.

Moreover, an outline of corrupt practices by the African Union Convention on Preventing and Combating Corruption and Related Offences (2003) include:

- a. The solicitation or acceptance, directly or indirectly by a public official or any other person, of any goods of monetary, or other benefit, such as a gift, favour, promise or advantage for himself or herself or for another person or entity, in exchange for any act or omission in the performance, of his or her public functions;
- b. The offering or granting, directly or indirectly, to a public official or any other person, of any goods of monetary value, or other benefit, such as gift, favour, promise, or advantage for himself or herself or for any other person or entity, in

- exchange for any act or omission in the performance of his or her public functions;
- c. The offering or granting, directly or indirectly, to a public official or any other person for the purpose of illicitly obtaining benefits for himself or herself or for a third party;
 - d. The diversion by a public official or any other person, for purposes unrelated to those for which they were intended, for his or her own benefit or that of a third party, of any property belonging to the state or its agencies, to an independent agency, or to an individual, that such official has received by virtue of his or her position;
 - e. The offering or giving, promising, solicitation or acceptance, directly or indirectly, of any undue advantage to or by any other person, who directs or works for, in any capacity, a private sector entity, for himself or herself or for anyone else, for him or her to act or refrain from acting, in breach of his or her duties;
 - f. The offering, giving, soliciting or accepting, directly or indirectly, of any undue advantage to or by any person who asserts or confirms that he or she is able to exert any improper influence over the decision making of any person performing functions in the public or private sector in consideration thereof, whether the undue advantage is for himself or herself or anyone else, as well as the request, receipt or the acceptance of the offer or the promise of such an advantage, in consideration of that influence, whether or not the influence is exerted or whether or not the supposed influence leads to the unintended result;
 - g. Illicit enrichment;
 - h. The use of concealment of proceeds derived from any of the acts referred to in this article; and
 - i. Participation as a principal, co-principal, agent, investigator, accomplice or accessory after the fact, or in any other manner in the commission or attempted commission of, in any other collaboration or conspiracy to commit, any of the acts referred to in this article.

4. Causes of Corruption in Nigeria

Various authors have expressed divergent views on the causes of corruption although usually there is concurrence in the opinion of researchers on the causative factors of corruption. Corruption pervades virtually every sphere of life in Nigeria and it is practically impossible to enjoy any public service without one form of gratification or the other. Some of the causes of this deplorable state of affairs include:

1. Poor Salaries and Wages: Public officials earn poor salaries which are grossly inadequate to cater for their needs. They engage in illicit activities to augment their legitimate earnings.

2. Poverty: Similar to the foregoing factor, prevalence of poverty among the Nigerian masses make them exploit every situation to their selfish benefit, usually at the expense of all other Nigerians. Poverty is rife in Nigeria to the extent that Nigeria is ranked among the 20 poorest countries in the world.
3. High rate of unemployment and underemployment: Majority of Nigerian youths are unemployed. This makes them willing to connive with others to engage in corrupt practices.
4. Poor state of social security and lack of good pension scheme: Individuals engage in corrupt practices in order to invest for the rainy day which is not adequately provided for by government and makes young individuals willing to go to any length to put some money by for future use.
5. Erosion of core cultural values: Deterioration in adherence to such social values of diligence, dignity, honesty etc lure young members of society to embrace pervasive social vices such as corruption which is seen now as a means of amassing wealth. Materialism has become the order of the day and nobody cares about sources of affluence flaunted by individuals.
6. Monoculture: The Nigerian economy which depends solely on oil money encourages public officials to loot the national purse.
7. Government's lack of will power to fight corruption: Public figures indicted for embezzling huge amounts of public funds easily get away with it.

5. Effects of Corruption

Corruption portends grave national consequences if it is not quickly addressed. It is a cankerworm that has eaten deeply into the delicate fabrics of the Nigerian society. Some of the effects of corruption in the Nigerian society which are not exhaustive include:

- Poor infrastructural development which has engendered inadequate power supply which in turn hampers national development (Egwemi, 2012; Imhonopi & Urim, 2013).
- Poor national security as a result of poor economy. This has led to wanton destruction of lives and property (George-Genyi, 2013).
- It imperils democratic governance. This has made possible the incursion of the military into politics, an aberration, with its attendant drawbacks (Egwemi, 2012; Otoghile, Igbafe & Agbontaen, 2014).
- It reduces the standard of goods and services available in the country because corruption condones adulteration of goods (Makinde, 2013).
- It reduces public spending on basic infrastructure such as roads, health facilities etc (Makinde, 2013).
- Capital flight to foreign countries which boosts foreign economies at the expense of local economy (Makinde, 2013; Odeh, 2014).
- It increases sectarian and ethnic bias (Makinde, 2013).

- It encourages brain drain when experts seek greener pastures overseas due to inclement living conditions at home (Otoghile, Igbafe & Agbontaen, 2014).
- It promotes materialism (Imhonopi & Urim, 2013).

6. Governance

Governance is considered as an ambiguous term which is susceptible to the crisis of universally agreed definitions. Varying perspectives on the connotation of governance make the concept all the more interesting. According to the World Bank (1992), *“governance refers to the manner in which power is exercised in the management of a country’s economic and social resources for development”*. This definition stresses the acquisition and use of public power to take decision on appropriation of resources and distribution of public goods. It can be considered as the use of economic, social and political powers vested in individuals, recognized by law in order to direct the affairs of state.

Onigbinde (2007) citing the Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) research project defined good governance as *“the process and institutions by which authority in a country is exercised; the process by which governments are selected, held accountable, monitored and replaced; the capacity of governments to manage resources efficiently and to formulate, implement and enforce sound policies and regulations; and, the respect for the institutions that govern economic and social interactions among them”*.

Simply put, governance infers the process of exercising political power to manage the affairs of a nation, which has such main elements as *“rule of law’ freedom of speech and association, free and fair election, accountability, probity and transparency and result oriented leadership*. (Adamolekun, 2000 in Lawal, Imokhuede and Johnson, 2012). Good Governance therefore involves the correct use of powers of state in making policies and enforcing the rule of law towards achievement of the common good.

Governance has also been defined by Ogundiya (2010) as *“the manner in which power is exercised by governments in the management and distribution of a country’s social and economic resources”*, by extension Ogundiya is of the opinion that governance might either be good or bad based on the normative context of how resources have been distributed to promote equality or otherwise. Furthermore, according to Lawal, Imokhuede and Johnson (2012) *“Governance means initiating, directing and managing public resources, organizing people and directing subordinates to put in their best to achieve good result in a given assignment”*. This infers that governance is all about ensuring that accountability is institutionalized in the allocation of public goods.

There is no doubt that Nigeria has enjoyed governance since independence, however the extent to which good governance prevailed in the last fifty-eight years is contentious as most of those years have been riddled with abysmal performance by office holders, whether military or civilian. Good governance is a state of affair which high level of competence and sincerity are displayed by leaders in the management of resources in meeting the needs and aspirations of the entire citizenry (Adeosun, 2012).

On a similar note, good governance is considered as all activities in the use of authority to manage the affairs of a country in such a way that all citizens freely achieve their legitimate interests and exercise their legal rights (UNDP, 1997).

It is obvious that development is at the heart of consideration of governance as being good or otherwise. In this regard, good governance was considered as the exercise of power in managing the economic and social resources of a nation towards achievement of sustainable development (World Bank, 1992). The World Bank (1989) further established some characteristics of good governance as: an efficient public service; an independent judicial system and legal framework to enforce contract; the accountable administration of public funds; an independent public auditor, responsible to a representative legislature; respect for the law and human rights at all levels of government; a pluralistic institutional structure; and a free press.

However, it is saddening that there appears to be a deficit of good governance in Nigeria because reasons advanced for perennial deficit of good governance in Nigeria include lack of rule of law; absence of development oriented leadership; absence of accountability and transparency; corruption challenges; as well as electoral malpractice challenges (Lawal, Imoukhuede & Johnson, 2012). Leadership at all levels of government is tainted with corruption. Makinde (2013) while corroborating the foregoing affirms that *"corruption is considered as the bane of governance in Nigeria"*. In fact, from inception of self-government in Nigeria to date, various governments and regimes have been indicted for varying degrees of corruption by leaders, whether civilian or military (Ike, 2010).

7. Nexus between Corruption, Good Governance and National Security

Pervasive corruption has profound effects on all facets of life in the Nigerian society. Good governance on the other hand is a veritable tool for development which is capable of eradicating corruption. Good governance thrives on such principles as justice, equity, freedom, liberty, accountability, openness, and transparency (Oluwole, 2003). It therefore implies that the application of these principles could inevitably eradicate corruption or minimize it to the barest minimum. Better still the, practice of good governance would eradicate corruption. Good governance is also a pre-requisite for national security. Corruption hampers rational and effective decision making on national security. It is parochial and only aims at satisfying selfish sentiments. Corruption affects national security in many ways such as making it difficult or impossible to enlist and train quality security operatives because bias is introduced in choosing candidates or because of paucity of funds to enlist and train the operatives.

Corruption also hampers national security because it facilitates easy access to deadly weapons by individuals or groups, for example, some corrupt military personnel sold military hardware to insurgents (Onuoha, 2009). Good governance eradicates corruption or minimizes it to the barest minimum. Good governance is also a

panacea to national insecurity because it fosters national development which enhances national security.

8. Conclusion

Pervasive corruption in all spheres of Nigerian life had hindered national development and thrown the majority of Nigerian masses into poverty. Successive governments have identified the polity's aversion to this vice, which continues to weaken the economy, and lashed on to it as a fast selling mantra to gain the confidence and support of the citizens, without necessarily doing enough to eradicate this vice. Stupendous proportion of national resources has so far been deployed, albeit wastefully, in establishing and running anti-corruption agencies like ICPC and EFCC to no avail.

Staggering dimensions of corruption always seem to burst out to make a travesty of anti-corruption wars being fought, so to say, by different regimes. A good example is that although the present President Muhammadu Buhari led APC government prides itself on routing corruption in Nigeria, it was scandalised by mind boggling cases of corruption established against two key actors of the regime, precisely the former Secretary to the Government of the Federation, Mr. Babachir David Lawal, and the former Director of the National Intelligence Agency (NIA), Ambassador Ayo Oke (Ifreke, 2017). The development has irked many Nigerians, who now seem resigned to fate that the anti-corruption war in Nigeria is absolutely intractable.

Good governance is a sine-qua-non for rapid national development. It also ensures equitable allocation of the national resources among citizens to cater for their diverse orientations, needs and aspirations. Such a situation would invariably culminate in a peaceful society in which security of lives and property is guaranteed. It therefore behoves all Nigerian citizens and stakeholders in all facets of the society to make concerted effort aimed at ensuring that good governance is entrenched at all cost.

8. Recommendations

Based on the foregoing, this paper proffers the following recommendations to eradicate corruption and bolster good governance in order to achieve national security:

1. Anti-corruption agencies such as Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) and Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC) should be repositioned, through adequate funding, to effectively conduct investigations leading to timely arrest, prosecution and sentencing of offenders as deterrent to others.
2. Government should intensify mass orientation campaign in the news media in order to eradicate corruption.
3. Potential crisis situations should be promptly diffused to avoid degeneration of such situations into full blown crisis which invariably poses avoidable threat to citizens' lives and property.

4. The educational curriculum should be reviewed in order to integrate into it new learning experiences, in such subjects like Social Studies and Civic Education, which promote good governance and national security while also eschewing corruption in all spheres of Nigerian society,
5. The legal framework should be reviewed to ensure that stiffer penalties are imposed and higher conviction rates are recorded in cases of corruption, as deterrent to potential offenders.
6. Political parties should embrace transparency in their choice of party candidates and avoid 'money politics' in order to avoid creating crises situations.
7. Government should ensure that merit is given premium in employment or appointment processes.
8. Accountability and transparency should be watchwords of any government.

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